

ISic1553

I.Sicily inscription 1553

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stucco

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰθι[]ασία ἤρ[υ]σα ἀγαθά

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284952

EDCS 41300027

PHI 175618

PHI 332686

PHI 336482

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 50.0993

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 42.1845

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 04.0043

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 23

Gabricsi, E. 1929. Stele sepolcrali di Lilibeo a forma di Heroon. *Monumenti Antichi*. 33: 41-60. At 55-56

Bisi, A.M. 1970. Influenze italiote e siceliote sull'arte tardo-punica. Le stele funerarie di Lilibeo. *Archeologia Classica*. 22: 92-130. At 101 no.5

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1553. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354416>